

**EXPLORING DIMENSIONS OF SLOW LIFE FILTERED
THROUGH SUSTAINABLE DESIGN**

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The following essay describes the efforts of the Studio titled “Exploring Dimensions of Slow Life Filtered through Sustainable Design,” as it was taught in the academic year of Fall 2009 and Spring 2010.

A. CONTEXT OF STUDIO WITHIN THE DEPARTMENT OF ARCHITECTURE

Fourth-Year Study Units

In the year 2009, the Department of Architecture of the University of Nicosia initiated a unique direction for its fourth-year students. Instead of a conventional thesis preparatory year of full academic studies followed by the fifth year where the thesis project is to be generated, the faculty created two Study Units from which the students entering their fourth year would have to choose from. Each Study Unit has a distinct area of concentration expressed within the framework of its related studio.

In addition to the Studio, each Unit is comprised of two supplementary courses where the students are exposed to theoretical and technical issues associated with Study Unit. The faculty undertaking responsibilities within each Study Unit are strictly selected for their expertise, knowledge and experience in the Unit’s area of study. In cases where no faculty member in the particular area of expertise was available, part-time faculty members were hired in a concerted attempt to maintain the highest standard of education within the Study Units.

Regardless of which Studio the students are registered to, they are all expected to follow all supplementary courses offered by both Units. This achieves a much-needed balance and uniformity among fourth-year studies. The Studio is a two-year commitment on behalf of both students and faculty. By their fifth-year, students are expected to have developed, expanded or isolated their fourth-year studio studies and promote them to a successful thesis.

Sustainable Architecture Unit

The Studio offered within the Sustainable Architecture_Unit is titled “**Exploring Dimensions of Slow Life Filtered through Sustainable Design**” and it shall be the main focus of this essay. As mentioned above, the Unit is comprised of the Studio course and the two associated supplementary courses. These two courses are History and Theory of Sustainable Architecture and Sustainable Design Practices. The History and Theory course offers a comprehensive understanding of the principles of sustainable architecture within a historical and socio-political context, whereas the Sustainable Design Practices course provides the necessary technical background and mechanics to succeed in creating sustainable architecture.

Studio Members

In the Fall semester of 2009, seven students with an interest in sustainable design enrolled in the Sustainable Architecture Unit Studio and three transfer students were placed in the Studio based on their individual academic interests. The Studio and two supplementary courses were taught by a collaborative unit of an architect and a landscape architect, each approaching the issue of sustainability from different perspectives, including bioclimatic architecture and innovative design, ecological systems and sustainable urbanism, and socio-economic issues pertaining to sustainable living.

B. PHILOSOPHY AND PERCEPTION

Slow Life and Sustainable Architecture

Waking up late... rushing to get dressed... forgetting to comb... no time for breakfast... rushing to the car or to the bus station... getting to work and then, rushing... and then some more...

What makes our life rush by so fast, what compels us to always be on the run? What inner need provides us with this momentum? Is it the need to compete, to achieve, to succeed?

Is the applied frequency emitted by our built environment subliminally feeding our impulse to rush?

We eat fast food, think fast thoughts, talk quickly to our friends and colleagues and inevitably, we create environments to match the fast rhythms of our lives.

We live fast lives and most likely design the appropriate architectural elements to accommodate us.

Take a moment and stand still.

Does food taste different when you chew while standing still? Does the ground under your feet feel softer? Does your breath feel cooler, stronger when taken in slowly and released slower still?

How does it feel to live slowly and enjoy all flavours of life? Savouring rather than devouring? Walking rather than running? Observing rather than judging?

Is slow life a virtue that can be identified within western lifestyle? Does it need to be juxtaposed to fast life for it to have a discernable meaning? How does sustainable living compare to slow and to fast living?

Does architecture have a measurable speed? How do we feel about our surrounding architecture? Can we identify slow and fast paces in our built environment?

These thoughts, expressed almost in a style of stream of consciousness, act as springboards for the foundation of the Studio's philosophy. In turn, these questions become the impetus for an entire set of other issues requiring students to investigate interpretations of slow life and fast life within the context of sustainable architecture. However, in order to progress successfully to this level of investigation, each student is first encouraged to develop his or her own idea of what sustainability means.

Slow life is primarily concerned with the analysis and reading of architectural dimensions as a conceptual framework for the presentation of significantly new, original and meaningful architectural ideas. The Studio explores the theoretical, the philosophical, the physical and the aesthetic qualities of *slowness* from life to architecture, their potential for making space and the emotional capacity of the spaces they make.

Philosophical Positions

Twenty years ago, sustainable architecture, since it was not included in conventional academic curricula, it was considered by most non-academics as a fad. Academics themselves looked upon it partly as a novelty, although

most certainly a worthy cause. Nowadays, where sustainability appears firmly in a large number of academic institutions, believers consider it a must and cynics consider it fashionable. The future generations, however, regardless of their philosophical persuasion, will most definitely consider it a necessity. Slowness, whether of living or of design, is an intriguing concept whose elusive nature encourages creative thought and sets numerous sceptical filters benefitting good design. Identifying, observing and evaluating slow life raises issues of perception on time and accountability to nature in ways that are intrinsic to sustainable design.

Let us try to playfully visualize all-things-architectural to be the product of a specific muscle group in the designer's subconscious. The muscle group is comprised of other smaller muscles which we can identify as "creativity," "practicality," "technical accuracy" etc. We can visualize the muscle at its earliest appearance in the subconscious mind, while it is still somewhat atrophied. Upon attending architecture school, the muscle is exercised and gradually starts functioning as a unit, all members flexing and contracting in unison producing a well-shaped, efficient muscle. Sustainable design and environmental responsibility customarily appear in the designer's subconscious as members of this "architectural" muscle group and together they have the potential to make the muscle stronger, more efficient and more resilient.

Since in the case of the Department of Architecture of the University of Nicosia, studies focusing on sustainable design officially enter the curriculum for the first time in the fourth year, regarding the principles of sustainability as part of the muscle group mentioned above may not be a realistic vision. In the course of a five year educational programme, it is probably safe to assume that the synergistic members of this muscle group have already been exercised into a shape by working together with method and system and any attempt for alterations may be met with resistance or with less than adequate results.

Consequently, the purpose of this Studio and the philosophical quest supporting the Sustainable Architecture Unit as a whole, given the circumstances of the Unit's conception, is not to enforce sustainable design and environmental responsibility as surrogate members of the muscle group. The purpose here is for these two principles to be the primary forces that help shape the muscle to fitness. They are not to be regarded as muscles, part of a larger unit of body, but as the weights, the dumbbells if you will, the design muscle is trained with in order to become more capable and resourceful. A timelier introduction of sustainable issues into the department's curriculum may be a more beneficial investment in the future of environmental culture in architecture schools, but such adaptations take time, patience and perseverance on behalf of academics and administrators alike.

Practical Extension

On a more tangible level, the mission of the Sustainable Architecture Studio is to elevate architecture and design to a coexistence of a harmonious and productive synergy of man, nature and the spirit of place. At the end of the studio journey, the students should be in a position to face their architectural identity in such a way where sustainable design will not represent an attachment or a supplement to their design principles, but both entities operate as an integrated process.

At the start of the studio journey, a foundation needs to be set where all attempts to define sustainability are put on the table and theories are taken into consideration. The global, multifaceted nature of sustainability is presented in such a way that students become aware of its ever-elusive definition and the range of disciplines it involves. This realization is inevitably faced by the students with some trepidation, so time is set aside for individual consultations helping students identify their own niche within the network of possibilities of sustainable design.

Sustainability is expressed not only as a healthy building technique but as a deep socio-political issue that transcends generations, race and social class. The Studio projects themselves, aim to explore the interdependency of issues of environmental, social and economic sustainability with students being prompted to develop individual, critical positions with regards to the broad concept of sustainability and to extend and explore those positions through their architectural design process.

C. STUDIO DESCRIPTION AND PEDAGOGICAL METHODS

Site Analysis

After the initial influx of new information regarding the philosophy, mechanics and application of sustainable architecture, the students need a means to feel grounded. For this reason, the first order of business is to establish familiarity with the proposed site and with the climatic and geographical circumstances that are specific to it.

The site chosen is a multifaceted one since it is a National Park located in a suburb of Nicosia, flanked by a university campus, the Nicosia General Hospital, a commercial complex and some residential districts. The paradoxical boundaries of this park make it a fascinating area of study with numerous possibilities and challenges whether the architectural intervention is a single building or a series of smaller, interrelated ones.

The students of the Studio are expected to develop their own brief – a good preparation for their self-directed thesis investigation which will follow in their fifth year of studies. Students in groups and individually, are called to examine the park in its entirety and to uncover its layers of complexity and potential. Shortcomings of the park are scrutinized and discussed in a productive and educational environment, while case studies are used to offer depth and perspective. During a guided class visit to the park, the students are called to investigate the site's literal characteristics but also to observe and document their own emotional responses.

Site analysis of the park and its surroundings is conducted in groups which produce a series of overlays pertaining to basic analytical issues such as land use, fauna and flora, circulation, geology and topography. Some groups may choose to examine issues of particular interest to them and produce relevant overlay maps. The finished product of base map and overlays is then scanned and made available to all students. Since this is the first contact some students experience with site analysis of this scale, they are encouraged to review the work of Ian McHarg and James LaGro. Once students are comfortable with the park's particulars, they are called to develop a masterplan for a theme park of their choice. This masterplan will serve them for the entirety of the year, since all their subsequent building interventions will be based on it.

Lectures , Guests and Critiques

Developing an understanding of design, maintenance and operation of the built environment while minimizing energy needs is a strong component of the Studio's objectives. These issues are presented to students by a series of in-studio lectures presented by the faculty and student peer presentations on case studies, technological advances and social issues. The basics of sustainable architecture, such as theory, ecology and technology are offered to the students through the two supplementary courses they take as part of their fourth-year curriculum.

The Sustainable Architecture Studio fosters a culture of diversity of opinion and constructive criticism. Throughout the duration of the studio year, a series of guest lecturers and critics offer their time and advice to individual students, evaluating each project's merits, providing intriguing stimuli, feedback and helping each student elevate his or her work to the next level. All desk critiques with guest lecturers are done in the presence of at least one of the studio instructors to better communicating class objectives and to facilitate communication.

Guest critics have included artists specializing on ecosystems, practicing architects focusing on bioclimatics and digital design and professors of relevant subjects from other local universities. Through their diverse educational background, the guest critics, some of whom studied and worked in countries such as Germany, Spain, Holland, England, USA and Greece, were also in a position to offer unique pedagogical perspectives.

Most studio days begin with a pinup of each student's work and his or her work is being discussed earnestly and constructively by fellow students and the instructors. As with all studios at University of Nicosia, there is a mid-semester review for all students where the entire faculty is invited as well as guest critics from other universities

and professionals. These reviews prove to be an excellent means of coordinating progress in all same-year studios and they provide an opportunity for students to benefit from the experience of a large scale presentation.

D. ASSIGNMENT STRUCTURE, EXERCISES AND PROJECTS

Students are assessed on the level of concentration they exhibit, their rigour and tenacity. Their subsequent grade is determined by the maturity with which they tackle problem analysis, the depth and commitment of their research work, the clarity of their thinking process, their creativity in generating ideas, application of mixed media skills, the quality of final product, progress and attendance.

First Semester

All projects assigned in the first semester have a distinct period of duration ranging from two to three weeks depending on the workload. As a result, students are encouraged to approach these projects as charrettes and work under rigid deadlines.

Site Analysis Assignment

Analyzing the site is a process that takes up the better part of the first studio month. The first assignment is the production of the site's base map and site analysis overlays and it is entirely focused on group work. This proves to be a great opportunity for student socializing, particularly since some students may have recently transferred from other schools. Students also develop a sense for handling group dynamics and conflict resolution.

Theme Park and Masterplan

Each student is expected to develop his or her own theme park based on his or her individual evaluation of the site's shortcomings, community needs and environmental betterment. The students choose a theme that is a challenge to them; one which they hope will lead them somewhere they have not been before. Students' individual tasks include:

- Exploration of thematic dimensions of the concepts of *slow* and *fast* (keeping notes, drawings, samples, cut-outs and anything else appropriate)
- Research and peer presentation on their chosen theme

During this time, students explore their theme in any creative way thinkable. This may include travelling, reading, drawing, talking, writing, film-making, performing, painting, writing stories and anything else which may or may not appear productive to their cause. The students are encouraged to take every opportunity to concentrate their efforts on comparisons and conclusions relating their theme and conceptual dimension of slow life. The projects will be generated from the creative observation and interpretation of the term *slow* either as a place, an object or an activity. The students' understanding and developed sensitivities will spawn much of their subsequent architecture. Their architecture must respond to environmental and sustainable demand, functionally as well as poetically.

The theme park is then translated to a masterplan in an appropriate scale. The plan is expected to exhibit mature decision-making with respect to citing functions and buildings as well as proper circulation provisions. No level of detail is expected, although free-hand mood shots or collages are encouraged to provoke students to imagine the attitude and the feel of the park.

Resting Points

The first habitable space students are called to design is a series of resting points whose location has already been established in the Masterplan. The resting points, intended as a spot where the park's visitors can take a break, represent the students' first attempt at a structure that follows basic principles of sustainable design. The design of the resting point structure must be such that it can be erected or installed at any point in the park, but can be adaptable and responsive to the particular location it is intended for.

The concept driving its design must be related to the park's proposed theme and must be consistent with the findings of the investigation of *slow*. The structure's area must not exceed 10m² and all passive and active solar design principles must be applied. The prototype must be responsive to climate, wind, sun and other particulars of the site and it must offer protection from the rain. Material investigation and selection is crucial.

Building 50-100m²

The second building assignment presents the challenge of maintaining all bioclimatic lessons learnt in the previous exercise and applying them to a larger area. The use of this building, intended to be unique within the masterplan, promotes a use relevant to the park's chosen theme. Choice of materials must be dealt with more perseverance, bringing forth topics such as material longevity, potential toxicity, recycling and reusing. Energy-saving technology is investigated as well as other established technologies demonstrating the principles of sustainable architecture and construction.

Building 500m²

The final assignment before the end of the first half of the Studio is a building larger in dimension to the two previous ones. The challenge of designing sustainably is now elevated to include architectural concerns such as access, entrance, space-use hierarchy, accommodation of auxiliary spaces, circulation and aesthetic acceptance within the natural landscape. Issues of cross-ventilation, orientation and exposure to natural sunlight are now examined more rigorously.

Review

While working on the three building assignments, the students approach the park in a greater level of detail and inevitably identify issues that need to be addressed on the level of the masterplan. At the end of the third building assignment and prior to the final review of the first semester, the students are compelled to revisit their masterplan and make all necessary corrections and adaptations based on lessons learnt during three assignments.

The first semester final review panels are present all major projects tackled during the semester, i.e. the masterplan and the three buildings as well as anything else the students deem necessary to their investigation. The panels are presented in A1 sheets and the students are instructed to make the panels as well-narrated as possible so as to require little or no explanation of the project's intentions.

Second Semester

Building 1,000m²

The final assignment of the Studio is a semester-long project, intended to exhibit all skills acquired and practiced in the three projects of the first semester. A more complex building is expected to be generated responding to issues of site specificity and sustainable design. Since energy performance is conventionally less efficient for larger-scale buildings, students also have the option to produce a complex of smaller buildings and to tackle the challenge of a mini urban environment surrounded by protected nature.

Before addressing their intervention, whether that is a building or a complex of buildings, the students are assigned an exercise to affectionately known as "site reconnaissance." This exercise is intended to bring students physically and intellectually close to the site of their proposed intervention. They are required to section their proposed site to a grid where each square has the approximate dimensions of 2mX2m. Then the students are called to investigate and document each grid as a microcosm, isolating particular characteristics present in most of the grids and proposing a possible hierarchy. Through this exercise the students are encouraged to develop their own language of reading the landscape of their site. Their findings are then presented in class in the form of a conceptual model, stationary or interactive, or in two-dimensional images.

Upon considering the final building, the following issues become relevant:

- Design dealing with complex environmental problems emphasizing the planning of large-scale buildings.
- Students are compelled to use their knowledge and experience of different constructional and structural models and their aesthetic properties to choose aptly and with sensibility from a range of possibilities.
- Students are also encouraged to consider how the luminous and acoustic aspects of design can be manipulated to facilitate the activities to be sheltered and explores how they can control objective mood and convey symbolic values.
- Human and social impact of the built environment of the inhabitants of the project's particular environment.
- Contemporary perspectives on the relationship between human behaviour, designed environments and energy efficiency. In effect, the final project explores the implications of those relationships for the purpose and future direction of design education, design research and design practice.
- Students become aware of design factors affecting indoor comfort and explore concepts, structures and techniques that lie behind the realization of energy conscious design.
- The link between quality of life and energy consumption, the variation in fossil fuel resources and end-use energy in Cyprus.
- The role of renewable energies in reducing environmental impact.

F. Critical Evaluation and Conclusions

Academic Year 2009-2010

If the degree of success of the Sustainable Architecture Studio is measured by students' enthusiasm, then the Studio was surely a triumph. During the course of the year, the students gradually became committed to the Studio's culture, as evidenced by the quality of their finished product, the degree of collaboration inspired among the group and the close bond fostered between the students and the two instructors.

A diversity of thematic projects were taken on such as skate board and cycling facilities, a dog park, a performance park, an educational centre, etc. A variety of subjects were tackled, including modularity, appropriate water purification technology, flexible occupancy and space reuse and issues of embodied energy. The Studio's standards were kept at a constantly challenging level and small number of students who were not able to keep up had to withdraw. Although all help was made available to them, the students decided on their own accord that they had more to gain by repeating the studio year.

The students were not only able to produce mature projects touching on all basic issues proclaimed by the Studio agenda, but most of them were able to greatly improve on their overall ability to solve complex architectural spaces and successfully present them in professional drawings and impressive computer renderings. This was partly the result of the instructors' perseverance and insistence that students should be handled as adults who are but a heartbeat away from professional employment.

Since this was the first year this Studio was offered, there were a series of valuable lessons to be learnt. It was established that the Studio's site was revealed to the students too early in the semester. In retrospect, it may have been wiser to allow students time to investigate sustainability and the *slow* dimension of its influence in architecture without the predisposition of a known site. The objectivity of these early research attempts may have produced a stronger, more focussed result if they were executed on a more universal background.

Another improvement the Studio will be striving towards in future years is to keep the slow life parameter closer and more apparent in the Studio process. Some students' research on slow life, regardless of how thoroughly it was initially executed, stayed in embryonic stages and was overshadowed by more tangible concerns such as derived from sustainable architecture. Conversely, one student opted to view slow life as a product of comparison and took on a project focussing on fast life. This was a welcome extension of the *slow* investigation and showed healthy initiative and creativity.

The Sustainable Architecture Studio was not only a prolific course for students and a valuable experience for the instructors; it proved to be a useful platform for discussion regarding pedagogical targets and techniques for fourth-year studios at the University of Nicosia. Since the completion of the 2010 academic year, the university's faculty has been using the knowledge and lessons learnt from the Studio as guidance in the objectives and planning of future studios. More importantly, the students' high level of product has become a datum on which students' projects are now being evaluated.